

NEW MEDIA LITERACY AND MISINFORMATION: SAMPLE OF THE UKRAINE-RUSSIA CRISIS

Mehmet Karanfiloğlu *

Summary

The Ukraine-Russia crisis, which recrudesced suddenly and affected the world agenda, started with the occupation of Ukraine by Russian military units on 24 February. This situation spread rapidly through new media opportunities, and many true or false news was made about it. While discussing whether this situation can be defined as a war, thousands of messages and news have spread daily through the new media. The accuracy of most of the information posted on social media platforms is controversial. Verification/fact-checking platforms began to work from the first day to check the accuracy of this critical information posted and transmitted new media opportunities. As in other examples, much fake and additional information that needs verification is shared regarding the Ukraine-Russia crisis. teyit.org and dogrulukpayi.com, the two fact-checking platforms, cope with verifying the information on this subject. Thus, it is possible to query, research and verify the remarkable information posted/circulated on new media platforms. Combating the processes defined as misinformation has become essential in realizing the dissemination of accurate information. In this context, this study focuses on misinformation activities and new media literacy. In addition, the findings obtained because of the research on fact-checking platforms, which are an effective counter-fight to the spread of false/fake news, are included. In this context, comparatively examined the posts on teyit.org and dogrulukpayi.com websites (on 24 February and 24 March 2022), which are the two most active fact-checking organizations.

Keywords: *New Media Literacy, Disinformation, Misinformation, Malinformation, Ukraine-Russia, Verification, Fact-Checking*

* Corresponding Author: Dr. Instructor Member, Ibn Haldun University, Faculty of Communication
mehmet.karanfiloglu@ihu.edu.tr. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4895-4220

Received Date: 20.08.2022 Accepted Date: 22.08.2022 Release Date: 30.09.2022

Atıf Bilgisi / Reference Information

Karanfiloğlu, M. (2022). Kolombiya Sineması ve Karşıtlıkların Gölgesinde Bir Seyir Deneyimi: Şiddet, Hafıza ve Ulus, Türkiye Medya Akademisi Dergisi. Cilt:2 Sayı:4, s. 123-145.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7111191>

YENİ MEDYA OKURYAZARLIĞI VE MEZENFORMASYON: UKRAYNA-RUSYA KRİZİ ÖRNEĞİ

Mehmet Karanfiloğlu*

Özet

Bir anda patlak veren ve dünya gündemini etkisi altına alan Ukrayna-Rusya krizi, 24 Şubat'ta Rus askeri birliklerinin Ukrayna'yı işgali ile başlamıştır. Bu durum yeni medya olanakları vasıtası ile hızla yayılmış, hakkında pek çok doğru veya yanlış haber yapılmıştır. Tüm dünyada bu durumun bir yandan savaş olarak tanımlanıp tanımlanmayacağı tartışılırken her gün binlerce mesaj ve haber yeni medya aracılığı ile yayılmaya başlamıştır. Özellikle sosyal medya platformları üzerinde paylaşılan bilgilerin pek çoğunun doğruluğu tartışmalı durumdadır. Yeni medya olanakları vasıtasıyla paylaşılan bu kritik bilgilerin doğruluğunu kontrol üzere bilgi-doğrulama/teyit platformları çalışmalarına ilk günden itibaren başlamıştır. Başkaca örneklerinde olduğu üzere Ukrayna-Rusya krizine yönelik de pek çok yanlış, doğrulanmaya muhtaç bilginin paylaşıldığı görülmektedir. teyit.org, dogrulukpayi.com olmak üzere iki bilgi-doğruma platformunda da bu bilgilerin teyit edildiği görülmektedir. Böylece yeni medya platformlarında paylaşım/dolaşıma sokulan dikkat çekici bilgilerin sorgulanması, araştırılması ve doğrulanması süreçlerinin gerçekleştirilmesi mümkün olabilmektedir. Mezenformasyon olarak tanımlanan süreçlerle mücadele etmek doğru bilginin yayılımını gerçekleştirmek bakımından önemli hale gelmiştir. Bu bağlamda bu çalışma, mezenformasyon faaliyetleri ile yeni medya okuryazarlığı konusuna odaklanmaktadır. Ayrıca, yanlış/yalan haberin yayılımı ile mücadelede etkili bir karşı savaş veren bilgi-doğrulama platformları üzerine yapılan araştırma sonucu elde edilen bulgulara yer verilmektedir. Bu kapsamda en aktif iki bilgi-doğrulama organizasyonu; teyit.org ve dogrulukpayi.com web sitelerinde yer alan ve 24 Şubat- 24 Mart 2022 tarihleri arasında doğruluğu teyit edilen paylaşımlar kıyaslamalı olarak incelenmiş ve bulgular paylaşılmıştır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yeni Medya Okuryazarlığı, Dezenformasyon, Mezenformasyon, Malenformasyon, Ukrayna-Rusya, Teyit, Bilgi Doğrulama.

* Sorumlu Yazar: Dr. Öğr. Üyesi, Ibn Haldun Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi, mehmet.karanfiloglu@ihu.edu.tr. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4895-4220

INTRODUCTION

On the axis of digital transformation and developments, it is increasingly exposing the world to the impact of new media platforms. New media opportunities appeal to increased users, and the dissemination of information/news transpires through these tools. New media seems advantageous in obtaining faster and more effective communication tools; contrarily, it is disadvantageous in terms of allowing false information/fake news to spread. Increasingly incorrect information is applied daily, especially on social media, which is one of the new media tools.

On the other hand, various organizations have established different platforms to prevent this situation. These organizations, called information-verification platforms, use multiple techniques to check the accuracy of the information shared in the new media environment. By circulating accurate information as a reverse action, they are fighting against all types of misleading information activities (disinformation, misinformation, and malinformation). This disseminating of verified information is desired to prevent the spread of false information/fake news.

In today's circumstances, information consumption of individuals constitutes uncontrollably, and that may come-to-be more traumatic with an increasing number of users. Communities that congregate and act without verifying the accuracy of the information may catalyze unavertable public events. Increasing misleading information activities may induce even more critical situations, especially during public events.

New media literacy has become a necessity, and individuals must distinguish between accurate and incorrect information. Moreover, new media literacy is necessary to produce content for the new media channels and select incoming information/news from the new media sources. Individuals who are illiterate in the new media become more likely to be exposed to misleading information activities. Consequently, with incipient media literacy, it will be possible to obviate misinformation on prominent issues for societies and to lay the substructure for more salubrious and more prudent communities.

FACT-CHECKING AND VERIFICATION: ON THE JOURNEY FROM MEDIA LITERACY TO NEW MEDIA LITERACY

In the past and today, the media is a collection of indispensable tools for transferring and disseminating information/news. Due to the dozens of news, information, and comments from the new media, standard or opposing views of individuals, organizations, and societies may transpire in the face of developing events and circumstances. On that account, the media is considered a factor that separates and unites organizations and individuals living as a society. Thus, with its unifying and dividing features, the new media always stands as a tool that should be read carefully.

Aiming to comprehend the incipient new media literacy, an expeditious brief of media literacy lightens the intricate structure of the subject. Media literacy is about reading and understanding flowing messages of the media sources and analyzing the message contents of the examination. News from the press has the power to create certain perceptions of individuals and society by sending certain types of manipulative or malicious intended messages. The continuity of messages flowing from the media impacts the perception's depth, intention, and qualification. As a consequence, the media messages are transmitted from various media sources on purpose and with continuity. Inversely, the individuals who have received flowing messages recognize and perceive the first signals, furthermore analyze those messages from the media sources under the pressure and guidance of biological and societal assertiveness in a complex environment. The impact of media literacy varies depending on factors, namely the quality, complexity, duration, length, and repetition of the content flowing from the media sources in specific predicamental. According to Hobbs, when thinking about a text such as a movie, commercial or television show; who sent the message, what the author's intention was, what techniques were applied to prepare the distinctive elements in the text, which lifestyles and perspectives were represented in the message, how the opposite views would interpret this text, and what the text acquired to convey are also determinative (2007, p. 9).

included in social life with computers, mobile phones, tablets, and smart televisions. All these tools are considered new media technologies and shall not be considered independent of the internet.

As with traditional media tools, changing opportunities with technology creates new media opportunities that are non-constitute obstacles to the continuation of the media-power relationship. Moreover, power holders who want to hold it with new media opportunities may achieve this at a lower cost. Bolter and Grusin (1998) explain this situation, noting that the new media has augmented conventional media; in other words, the transfer of the existing printed newspaper to digital in the network environment cannot be interpreted as a new scenario yet as an improvement that preserves with high-technology advancement. Hence, the monopoly position of traditional media in society and its power relationship with the internet has initiated a very fragmented structure. In contrast to the one-way function of traditional media in the communication process, the author classifies the potential of the interaction of the new media as asynchronous and demassifying, that is, an area under his control, specific to each individual (Geray, 2003).

The time and space-independent character of the new media make the information/news accessible from elsewhere. The internet's increase in interaction allows the individual to freely choose from the complete information available in total channels and share any content from their social media account through their own media channel. Thus, new media users perceive, interpret, and select incoming information in proportion to their new media literacy level; in integration, it can apportion these contents as its engendering and direct its dissemination to a broader area.

In this context, the ability to share information/news on the new media and its access has moved new media users from a passive position to an active one; recently, new media users may choose, like, and share information/news as content in the milieu, such as on social media platform; thus, it evolves into social media content and open to interaction.

On the other side, news production may be accomplished by journalists and non-journalists in the new media environment. For this reason, journalism and its practices

were profoundly affected. With blogs and social media applications such as Facebook and Twitter that started to spread with the internet, users who were passive consumers in the past began to interact with other users to produce content jointly, make their news, and apply/share them on the network. In this sense, professional journalism has also transformed; mainstream media organizations have benefited from interactive and multimedia features such as video, photography, and commentary (Newman, 2009). Adaptation to the structure based on the interaction of the cyber environment in the new media; has eliminated the news production process of the monopoly of professional journalists; with the ease of access to information, alternative media initiatives of citizens and communities contributed to polyphony and democratization of the communication environment (Rodríguez, 2008). In this respect, the new media includes what is necessary for the foundations of a more democratic society with its unique features.

On the contrary, some unfavorable situations were encountered with the new media. Along with this comes problems such as decreasing privacy, increasing information, and the increase in false or fake news, cyberbullying, cyber fraud activities, cyber terrorism, and even cyber war threats. In other words, besides the positive effects of the internet and social media on social life, the other side of the coin is unbrilliant. These can be summarized as personal privacy damaged in the online environment, discrimination suffered by those that are inaccessible to the network society, the limitations of the internet's promise of global democratization, cyber-bullying, cyber-terrorism, censorship equipped with technical means and hidden among algorithms, and colossal disinformation (manipulation) (Bauman & Lyon, 2013; Morozov, 2011).

With its increasing threats, the new media caused many incidents. Cambridge Analytica scandal, Facebook data scandal, US presidential elections, the news after the separation of the United Kingdom from the European Union, which is called Brexit, popular uprisings in northern Africa and the middle east, defined as the Arab spring, yellow vests protests in France, Gezi Park protests in Turkey and, finally, social events such as during the COVID-19 pandemic process are listed among the negative aspects of new media. Post-truth, defined as the objective reality being less practical than

personal beliefs and emotions in forming a public opinion, has also been discussed in this context (Keyes, 2004).

As an information source, its features, such as the constant flow of information and the opportunity to reach millions of people quickly, easily, and at a meager cost, may often cause social media to face harsh criticism and accusations. Social media, which is primarily anonymous, unlike traditional media's institutional structure, is highly open to manipulation (Filibeli & Şener, 2019, p. 492; Eren & Aydın, 2014, p. 203). When considered from this point of view, new media literacy is quite essential, just like media literacy that is highlighted in traditional media (Çömlekçi & Başol, Sosyal medya haberlerine güven ve kullanıcı teyit alışkanlıkları üzerine bir inceleme, 2019).

One application that has become increasingly popular lately and distinguished regarding new media literacy is verification or information-verification platforms. These platforms research the accuracy of news/information circulated in new media by independent organizations. In a nutshell, users will doubt the authenticity of the news presented to them in the face of fake news and information through new media literacy skills and thus distinguish between fake news and truth (Kutlu & Doğan, 2020, p. 87). In this way, individuals can be protected from the misinformation activities they will be exposed to while reading about the new possibilities of digitalized media.

Fact-checking platforms (teyit.org, dogrulukpayi.com, malumatfurus.com), utilized by users to verify the accuracy of the news/information and the arguments in the news, established to combat fake news, are gaining importance daily. One of the primary missions of these platforms is to inform users about the reliability of digital news, and thereby, it is aimed to ensure that the public is informed accurately, that opinions are formed within the scope of objective news and facts, and that users are less exposed to disinformation (Çömlekçi, 2019, p. 1553). As a result, users may accomplish verification behavior by being suspicious of the fake news they are exposed to on social media and draw the distinction between fake news and real news more clearly (Kutlu & Doğan, 2020, p. 87).

Nonetheless, it shall not be overlooked that; being able to distinguish between real and fake news is an exceedingly complex and time-consuming task; even only one piece

of news may require verification by spending long hours and by a team. As a reader or user, verifying news coming through new media every time can be perceived as problematic or undesirable.

At the other end, news on new media may be circulated voluntarily or involuntarily; this makes it difficult to sort and differentiate inaccurate information. There are discourses on the inaccuracy of three types of information in the literature: Disinformation, Misinformation, and Malinformation. Disinformation; is the deliberate dissemination of false information; misinformation; is information that is imprecise and open to more than one understanding and use; malinformation, contrary, is the definition used to circulate sensitive, strategically, accurate information for dissemination to generate benefits (D'Amorim & Miranda, 2021, p. 9). As can be seen, more than one type of misleading information activity is encountered; and dis-, mis- and mal-information have categories. According to Wardle (2017), these categories are listed as follows:

- Manipulation
- Misleading content
- False connection
- Fabricated content
- Imposter
- False context
- Parody /satire

Misleading information activities listed above are the terminologies used to classify the methods and techniques used, while there are some false information/news may be evaluated under one of these categories or several. Therefore, too much classification and categorization may cause understanding the situation even more challenging.

The increase in the production and circulation of fake news has a profound effect on the formation of a post-truth era; another critical factor is that people believe in comments containing fake or false information to hold tight to their views and beliefs,

mistake the words for truth or close themselves to different ideas. At this point, media literacy emerges as a method of struggle that will enable users to adopt a critical approach to fake news/information; and, therefore, the reality of how critical new media literacy is. Academes and media professionals acknowledge the importance and necessity of media literacy (Kavaklı, 2019, p. 673); in this context, new media literacy competencies and information verification platforms appear. According to Buckingham, new media literacy has four aspects: representation, language, production, and audience/reader/user (2007, p. 48). Perceiving and understanding incoming messages in the direction of these four directions with the five WS and one H procedure, it becomes crucial to notice representations and develop critical thinking competencies. According to Hobbs (2010, p. 18), the essential competencies of digital and media literacy and the skills that individuals should have been listed as follows:

- Access,
- Analyze and evaluate,
- Create,
- Reflect,
- Act.

In order to become a new media literate, it is required to use skills to find and employ media and technology tools, share appropriate and relevant information with others, assess the potential effects or results of messages, and operate messages and critical thinking to analyze message quality, accuracy, reliability, and perspective. In addition, producing or creating content with the awareness of the target audience and composition techniques, using creativity and self-confidence in self-expression, applying social responsibility and ethical principles to one's own identity, life experience, communication behavior, and attitudes, and sharing information and sharing information in family, workplace, social groups are required. To overcome all these challenges, working individually and collaboratively, and participating as a community member operating at local, regional, national, and international levels may be helpful.

For its part, when considering internet news/information fact-checking/verification platforms in Turkey, few platforms exist, and those enterprises

such as *doğruluk-payı*, *yalan-savar*, *teyit*, and *malumatfuruş* maintain a stance against the misleading information activities that accompany the new media by doing fact-checking (Foça, 2016). The platform of *dogrulukpayi.com* (2021) can be shown as the first attempt in this sense, and it was founded in 2014 as an initiative of the Association for Dialogue for a Common Future (In Turkish: *Ortak Gelecek için Diyalog Derneği*). The second platform of *malumatfuruş.org* (2019) was established in 2015; however, the third platform of *teyit.org* (2022) was established in 2016 as an independent initiative by Media Research. Although the second platform does not appear to be highly active, the third platform on its website states: on *teyit.org*; "we have been examining suspicious information on the internet since 2016, conducting educational activities to improve digital literacy and critical thinking skills, and bringing different actors together to address the problem of misinformation. We contribute to the development of sustainable solutions." Eventually, the last *yalansavar.org* (2022) platform, which is composed of volunteer staff for "investigating suspect and unsubstantiated allegations," is considered another inactive platform.

These platforms accomplish information/news verification upon various methods and techniques, most of which are based on using other facilities on the internet, changeable according to each news/information's content. A high number of other methods can be listed apart from standard methods, such as reverse image search, scanning, and verification via some intermediary software:

- Verification of information through other sources,
- Making use of search engines by using detailed/advanced search methods such as visual, audio, news, chronological,
- Deep web search
- Consulting the experts on the subject, asking the news subject,
- Watch the video, compare, check details, and match,
- Listening, comparing, analyzing audio recordings,
- Troll -bot account checking,
- Scanning official channels,
- Examining satellite images and street views,
- Archive scanning,

- Fact-checking software,
- Other fact-checking platforms.

RESEARCH

Method

This study aims to analyze the content of the shares created due to verifying news and claims, in the context of new media literacy, on two fact-checking organizations' websites: *teyit.org* and *dogrulukpayi.com* in Turkey. To determine the difference between the two platforms, we analyze the differences between those groups. A supported quantitative content analysis method was used.

The study reviewed ninety-four posts (Photo, text, video), and the researcher quantitatively coded them according to the meaning categories. The research model was created based on three levels identified in the "Personal Branding on Twitter" study by Brems et al. (2017). The content's type and platform at the first level, the verification of the information (fact-fake), and the misinformation category at the second level (Satire or parody, misleading content, imposer content, fabricated content, false connection, false context, manipulated content); at the third level, the amount and type of interaction are analyzed. As of the stated study, re-sharing such as (@Retweet) is to determine the interaction's amount and kind.

In line with the purpose of the research, the research questions are as follows:

- RQ 1: What platforms and content types do fact-checking organizations encounter while verifying during the crisis?
- RQ 2: What are the misinformation categories of news that fact-checking organizations did not verify during the crisis?
- RQ 3: What are the interaction types and content levels reviewed by fact-checking organizations during the crisis?
- RQ 4: During the crisis, is there a significant difference between the information categories of the verifiers on *teyit.org* and *dogrulukpayi.com*?

Sampling

This study analyzes the verification posts on the fact-checking platforms during the Ukrainian-Russia crisis, and news and posts assessed by fact-checking outlets are in different encodings. Two fact-checking media, teyit.org and dogrulukpayi.com, were examined and the posts discussed in the first month of the Ukrainian-Russia crisis are categorized. From the beginning of the problem, most detected misinformation types, the content of posts, platform information, and dissemination path in evaluated posts are analyzed. According to the research findings, the posts analyzed were ninety-four from 22 February 2022 to 22 March 2022. It was specified that ninety-three of these posts are fake.

Validity and Reliability

In the study, validity and reliability measures determined for qualitative research were applied. It is aimed to increase the validity and reliability of the study by using analyst variation (Patton, 1999, p. 1193), a purposive sampling method, and getting expert opinion (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2011).

Data Analysis

The coded data were analyzed with the SPSS 17.0 program. Frequency and percentage calculations were made to describe the data set, and the Mann-Whitney U test was applied to determine the difference between fact-checking platforms.

Findings

In this study, which emphasizes the importance of new media literacy, many posts were made concerning the subject on social media from the first moment military operations started. In parallel with it, fact-checking platforms have begun investigating the posts and revealed the findings. Although both platforms verify the posts' truth, they assess the matter in numerous ways. However, both platforms provide the source, type, content, misinformation categorization, and accuracy of the post. On the other hand, both platforms have highlighted social media platforms. Therefore, it may be possible to access interaction and share information on analyzed posts when shared on social media.

Fact-checking platforms report accuracy tests with various methods and techniques, such as reverse image search, archive scanning, benchmarking data, and finding the source. Thanks to those methods, they may verify the information's accuracy. Most of the posts in the study are on Twitter (81.91%), and the rest are on Facebook, websites, Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp. Its dispersal was like both fact-checking platforms and in the same order. Moreover, content types of rates are 46.8% from photos, 43.62% from videos, and 9.57% from texts.

Platform	<i>dogrulukpayi.com</i>		<i>teyit.org</i>		Both	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	Total	%
Twitter	39.00	90.70	38.00	74.51	77.00	81.91
Facebook	3.00	6.98	4.00	7.84	7.00	7.45
Websites	0.00	0.00	6.00	11.76	6.00	6.38
Instagram	1.00	2.33	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.06
TikTok	0.00	0.00	2.00	3.92	2.00	2.13
WhatsApp	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.96	1.00	1.06
Total	43.00	100.00	51.00	100.00	94.00	100.00

Table 1 Fact-Checking Platforms and New Media Types

teyit.org provides information about misinformation categorization in each analysis. On the contrary, *dogrulukpayi.com* only classifies the posts as fake, partially incorrect, and accurate. The researcher analyzes the misinformation categorization to match both platforms. Consequently, both platforms have found 70.21% false connection, 11.70% fabricated content, 7.45% manipulated content, 4.26% of misleading content, 3.19% false context, 1.06% parody/satire content. In this process, on both platforms, no imposter contents were found.

	<i>dogrulukpayi.com</i>						<i>teyit.org</i>					
	Photograph		Text		Video		Photograph		Text		Video	
	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%	<i>f</i>	%
False Context	9,5	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	16,7	0,0	0,0	9,5
Misleading Content	4,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	4,3	2,0	33,3	0,0	0,0	4,8
Accurate	4,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,8
False Connection	61,9	0,0	0,0	16,0	84,2	15,0	65,2	1,0	16,7	21,0	95,5	61,9
Manipulated Content	4,8	1,0	33,3	3,0	15,8	2,0	8,7	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,8
Parody/Satire	4,8	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	4,8
Fabricated Content	9,5	2,0	66,7	0,0	0,0	4,0	17,4	2,0	33,3	1,0	4,5	9,5
Unidentified	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	1,0	4,3	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0

100,0 3,0 100,0 19,0 100,0 23,0 100,0 6,0 100,0 22,0 100,0 100,0

Table 2 Fact-Checking Platforms and Dis-, Mis- and Mal-Information Categories

The Mann-Whitney-U test controlled the results of the examinations via both platforms, and no significant differences were found ($U = 33,00$; $p > 0.05$).

In other respects, social media platforms allow posts to interact in various aspects. On Twitter, they are the reply, retweet, like, and share; on Facebook, they are like or comment; on Instagram, it is like, comment, share and add to collection; on TikTok, they are like, comment and share. However, there are no specified interactions for websites. However, quoting/duplicating on all platforms (with various mentions and techniques; taking the screenshot, using #hashtag or @tagging) is frequently used. Considering the posts were analyzed by both fact-checking platforms, receiving (average) sharing (only retweeting) 4586 times and interaction 3691 times (on Twitter, Facebook, Instagram, and TikTok: like + comment). Averagely, receiving more shares than interaction leads to misinformation and fake news dissemination that supports the idea of the importance of new media literacy.

CONCLUSION

The tension between Ukraine and Russia and the subsequent war profoundly affected the world; millions of people had to migrate, and many were forced to live in harsh war conditions. The number of misleading information activities shared through new media opportunities before and during the war continues to increase following the events, and this situation may serve many disadvantageous situations, up to the misperception of the events, their interpretation, and wrong decisions.

Appropriate use of new media opportunities and prevention of false information/news may only be feasible with new media literacy, yet, as can be seen in the case of Ukraine-Russia, recognizing false information/news and applying precautions against misleading information activities progress in direct proportion to new media literacy skills. Although it is a controversial issue that every message from the media may be wrong intentionally or unintentionally, it is undeniable that much fake or false information is shared in the media.

From this point of view, fact-checking platforms are essential in verifying information/news; therefore, examining the shared, flowing information/news verification posts by such platforms in the context of the Ukraine-Russia crisis provides vital information. In this regard, the research study on teyit.org and dogrulukpayi.com reveals that it detects the same type of categorical dis-, mis-, and malinformation on both platforms. Even under challenging conditions such as war, false information or fake news was circulated, especially by posts on social media platforms. Especially in the category of erroneous association using photo and video content, data accumulation on both platforms shows that visual content is in a critical position in sharing inaccurate information/news.

Consequently, as with media literacy, how critical new media literacy is for societies and individuals has been understood again with these research findings. Information verification methods and techniques learned with new media literacy have become essential in protecting individuals from false information/news.

REFERENCES

- Avşar, Z. (2013). *Medya Okuryazarlığı*. İletişim ve Diplomasi, 2(5), 5-17.
- Bauman, Z., & Lyon, D. (2013). *Akışkan Gözetim*. (E. Yılmaz, Trans.) İstanbul: Ayrıntı Yayınları.
- Bolter, J. D., & Grusin, R. A. (1998). *Remediation: Understanding New Media*. MIT Press.
- Buckingham, D. (2007). Digital Media Literacies: Rethinking Media Education in The Age of The İnternet. *Research in Comparative and International Education*, 2(1), 43-55.
- Çömlekçi, M. F. (2019). Sosyal Medyada Dezenformasyon ve Haber Doğrulama Platformlarının Pratikleri. *Gümüşhane Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi Elektronik Dergisi*, 7, 1549-1563.
- Çömlekçi, M. F., & Başol, O. (2019). Sosyal Medya Haberlerine Güven ve Kullanıcı Teyit Alışkanlıkları Üzerine Bir İnceleme. *Galatasaray Üniversitesi İletişim Dergisi*, 30, 55-57.
- D'Amorim, K. S., & Miranda, M. K. (2021). Misinformation, Disinformation, and Malinformation: Clarifying The Definition And Examples In Disinfodemic Times. *Encontros Bibli*, 26, 1-23. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5007/1518-2924.2021.e76900>
- dogrulukpayi.com. (2021, Jan 11). Hakkımızda. Retrieved from Doğruluk Payı: <https://www.dogrulukpayi.com/sayfa/hakkimizda>
- Eren, V., & Aydın, A. (2014). Sosyal medyanın kamuoyu oluşturmadaki rolü ve muhtemel riskler. *KMÜ Sosyal ve Ekonomik Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 16(1), 197-205.
- Filibeli, T. E., & Şener, O. (2019). Manipüle Edilmiş Enformasyonel Bir Vitrin be Popülist Bir Enformasyon Alanı Olarak Twitter. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi Kültürel Çalışmalar Dergisi*, 6(2), 492-515.
- Foça, M. A. (2016, Dec 08). Avrupa'da fact-checking: doğrulama demokrasinin yeni bekçisi mi? Retrieved from teyit.org: <https://teyit.org/avrupada-fact-checking-dogrulama-demokrasinin-yeni-bekcisi-mi>

- Geray, H. (2003). *İletişim ve Teknoloji*. Ankara: Ütopya Yayınevi.
- Hobbs, R. (2007). *Reading the Media: Media Literacy in High School English*. Newyork: Teachers College, Columbia University.
- Hobbs, R. (2010). *Digital and Media Literacy: A Plan of Action*. Washington, D.C., USA: The Aspen Institute.
- Kavaklı, N. (2019). Yalan Haberle Mücadele ve İnternet Teyit/Doğrulama Platformları. *Erciyes İletişim Dergisi*, 6(1), 663-682.
- Keyes, R. (2004). *The Post-Truth Era: Dishonesty and Deception in Contemporary Life*. St. Martin's Press.
- Kim, J., Namkoong, K., & Chen, J. (2020). Predictors of Online News-Sharing Intention in The U.S And South Korea: An Application of The Theory of Reasoned Action. *Communication Studies*, 71(2), 315-331.
- Kutlu, A., & Doğan, E. (2020). Kesin Bilgi, Yayalım: Hakikat Sonrası Çağda Yalan Haberlere İlişkin Y Kuşağının Tutum ve Davranışları. *Akdeniz Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi Dergisi*, 34, 83-101.
- malumatfurus.org. (2019). Hakkında. Retrieved from malumatfurus.org: <http://www.malumatfurus.org/hakkinda/>
- Morozov, E. (2011). *The Net Delusion: The Dark Side of Internet Freedom*. TN, USA: Public Affairs.
- Newman, N. (2009). *The Rise of Social Media and Its Impact on Mainstream Journalism*. . University of Oxford: Reuters Institute for the Study of Journalism.
- Patton, M. Q. (1999). Enhancing the quality and Credibility of qualitative analysis. *HSR: Health Service Research*, 34(5 Pt 2), 1189–1208.
- Rodríguez, C. (2008). *Citizens' Media*. The International Encyclopedia of Communication.
- teyit.org. (2022). Nedir? Retrieved from teyit.org: <https://teyit.org/nedir>

- Wardle, C. (2017, February 17). Fake News. It's Complicated. Retrieved from First Draft: <https://medium.com/1st-draft/fake-news-its-complicated-d0f773766c79>
- yalansavar.org. (2022). Yalansavar – Sık Sorulan Sorular. Retrieved from yalansavar.org: <https://yalansavar.org/yalansavar-sik-sorulan-sorular/>
- Yegen, C. (2018). Doğru Haber Alma Hakkı ve Sosyal Medya Dezenformasyonunu Doğruluk Payı ve Yalansavar ile Tartışmak,. *Erciyes İletişim Dergisi*, 5(4), 101-121.
- Yıldırım, A., & Şimşek, H. (2011). *Sosyal Bilimlerde Nitel Araştırma Yöntemleri*. Ankara: Seçkin Yayıncılık.

GENİŞLETİLMİŞ ÖZET

Dijital dönüşüm ve sonrasında yaşanan gelişmelerin paralelinde, tüm dünyada yeni medya platformlarının etkisine daha çok rastlanılır hale gelinmiştir. Yeni medya olanakları; artan kullanıcı sayılarını ve muazzam ölçeklerde bilgi/haber akışını beraberinde getirmiştir. Bu bakımdan yeni medya araçlarının daha hızlı ve daha etkili iletişim sonuçları elde etmek gibi avantajları bulunsa da sahte bilgilerin/haberlerin yayılmasına olanak tanımak bakımından dezavantajlı bir konumdadır. Her gün, özellikle de yeni medya araçlarından biri olan sosyal medyada giderek daha çok yanlış bilginin/haberin yayıldığına şahit olmaktayız.

Bu durum karşısında, çeşitli kuruluşların yanlış bilginin yayılımını önlemek amacıyla çalışmalar yapabilmek için farklı platformlar oluşturduğunu görmekteyiz. Bilgi doğrulama platformları adı verilen bu kuruluşlar, yeni medya ortamında paylaşılan bilgilerin doğruluğunu kontrol etmek için birden fazla teknik kullanarak ve tespit edilen sonuçları veya doğru bilgileri -tersi yönde bir eylem olarak- dolaşıma sokarak her türlü yanıltıcı bilgi kargaşası/bozukluğu (dezenformasyon, mezenformasyon ve malenformasyon) ile mücadele etmektedir. Bu kuruluşlar temel amacını; yanlışlarının yerine doğrulanmış bilgilerin yayılması ve yanlış bilgilerin/sahte haberlerin yayılmasını azaltmak olarak açıklamaktadır.

Günümüzde, bireylerin bilgi tüketimi kontrolsüz bir şekilde gerçekleşmekte ve bu durum giderek artan sayıda kullanıcı ile daha da travmatik bir hal alabilmektedir. Bilgilerin doğruluğunu sorgulamadan toplu hareket eden bireylerin toplumsal olayları tetiklemesi geçmişte pek çok örnekle tecrübe edilmiştir. Yanıltıcı bilgi kargaşası/bozukluğu, özellikle toplumsal olaylar esnasında veya toplumu ilgilendiren önemli konularda çok daha kritik sonuçlara sebebiyet verebilmektedir.

Tüm bu sebeplerden yeni medya okur yazarlığının ne denli önemli bir konu olduğu ve bireylerin doğru-yanlış bilgileri ayırt etmesinin ne kadar kritik bir konumda olduğu gerçeği ile karşı karşıya kalmaktayız. Bu sebeple, yeni medya kaynaklarından gelen bilgileri/haberleri seçebilmek, anlamak, yorumlamak ve yeni medya araçları için içerik üretmek gibi basamakları bilmek gerekli hale gelmektedir. Çünkü yeni medya okuryazarlığı bağlamında okuyazar olmayan bireylerin yanıltıcı bilgi kargaşasına/bozukluğuna maruz kalma olasılığı artmaktadır. Yeni medya okuryazarlığı; toplumların ve bireylerin gündemdeki konular ve sorunlar hakkında doğru bilgi sahibi olmak ve daha ihtiyatlı davranabilmek için ihtiyaç duyacağı bilgi, yöntem ve uygulamaları sunmaktadır.

24 Şubat itibariyle başlayan ve dünya gündemini bir anda saran etkisiyle Ukrayna-Rusya krizi, sosyal medyanın da etkisiyle hızla tüm dünyada konuşulur hale gelmiştir. Çeşitli kaynaklarda “2022 Rusya'nın Ukrayna'yı İşgali”, “Ukrayna'nın ‘askerden ve Nazizm'den arındırılması’ amacıyla başlattığı askerî operasyon”, “Ukrayna-Rusya Savaşı” veya “Gerilim” olarak tanımlanan bu krizde, sosyal medya paylaşımlarıyla pek çok doğru veya yanlış bilginin yayılımına tanık olunmuştur. Ancak başkaca örneklerinde de olduğu üzere, sosyal medya platformlarında paylaşılan Ukrayna-Rusya krizine yönelik pek çok yanlış, doğrulanmaya muhtaç bilginin paylaşıldığı görülmektedir.

Bu araştırma, Ukrayna-Rusya krizi sırasında sosyal medya üzerinde paylaşılan bilgilerin/haberlerin doğruluğunu kontrol eden platformlardaki (teyit.org ve dogrulukpayi.com) doğrulama paylaşımlarını analiz etmektedir. Bu iki platform üzerinde gerçekleşen Ukrayna-Rusya krizine yönelik yapılan paylaşımlar incelenerek birçok açıdan kategorize edilmiştir. Öte yandan her iki platform da doğrulama sonrası elde edilen bulguları çeşitli yönlenden kategorize etmektedir. Bu kategorizasyonlar da kıyaslamalı olarak çalışmaya dahil edilmiştir. Araştırma kapsamında iki platformun da 22 Şubat 2022 - 22 Mart 2022 tarihleri arasındaki tüm paylaşımları incelenmiş ve toplamda doksan dört adet veri toplanmıştır. Platformlarca incelenen bu paylaşımların doksan üçünün yanlış/sahte olduğu tespit edilmiştir.

İncelenen paylaşımlar şu üç türden oluşmaktadır: Fotoğraf, metin ve video. Üç türden gerçekleşen paylaşımlar, anlamsal kategorilerine göre kantitatif olarak kodlanmıştır. Araştırmanın modeli, Brems ve Al. (2017) tarafından "Twitter'da Kişisel Markalama" çalışmasında tanımlanan üç seviyeye dayanarak oluşturulmuştur. Birinci düzeyde paylaşılan içeriğin türü ve kaynağı, ikinci düzeyde doğrulanma bilgisi (doğruyanlış) ve yanlış bilgi kategorisi (Parodi- *Parody/Satire*, Çarpıtma- *Misleading Content*, Taklit- *Imposter Content*, Uydurma- *Fabricated Content*, Hatalı İlişkilendirme- *False Connection*, Bağlamdan Koparma- *False Context*, Manipülasyon- *Manipulated Content*); üçüncü düzeyde ise ne miktarda ve hangi türde etkileşim sağlandığı analiz edilmiştir. Belirtilen çalışma ile paralel olarak etkileşimin miktarı ve türünün belirlenmesinde orijinalindeki yanıtlar yerine tekrar paylaşma (@Retweet) baz alınmıştır.

Çalışmada, nitel araştırmalar için belirlenen geçerlilik ve güvenilirlik önlemleri uygulanmıştır. Analistin varyasyonu (Patton, 1999, s. 1193), amaçlı örnekleme yöntemi ve uzman görüşü (Yıldırım ve Şimşek, 2011) yöntemleri kullanılarak çalışmanın geçerliliğini ve güvenilirliğini artırmayı amaçlamaktadır. Kodlanmış veriler SPSS 17.0 programı ile analiz edilmiştir. Frekans ve yüzde hesaplamaları veri kümesini tanımlamak için yapılmıştır ve doğrulama platformları arasındaki farkı belirlemek için Mann-Whitney U testi uygulanmıştır.

Genel olarak, bilgi doğrulama platformları; tersine görsel/görüntü arama, arşiv tarama, karşılaştırmalı verileri ve kaynakları bulma gibi çeşitli yöntem ve tekniklerle doğruluk testlerini gerçekleştirmekte ve bunu yayınlamaktadır. Paylaşılan yanlış bilgi içeriği çeşitlendikçe bilgi doğrulama yöntemi de değişebilmekte ve paylaşılan platforma göre farklı uygulamalar gerçekleştirilebilmektedir. Çalışmadaki gönderilerin çoğu Twitter'da (%81.91) ve geri kalanı; Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, WhatsApp'ta ve diğer web sitelerinde dolaşıma sokulmuştur. Ayrıca içerik türleri; yüzde 46.8'i fotoğraflardan, yüzde 43.62'si videolardan ve yüzde 9.57'si metinlerden oluşmaktadır.

Analiz edilen platformlardan ilki *teyit.org*; her analizde Warldle'nin (2017) yanlış bilgi kategorizasyonu kullanarak gönderileri sınıflandırmaktadır. İkinci platform ise, *dogrulukpayi.com* gönderileri yalnızca “sahte, kısmen hatalı ve doğru” olarak sınıflandırmaktadır. Ancak yine de paylaşılan içeriklerde Warldle'nin (2017) yanlış bilgi kategorilerinden bahsedilmektedir. Bu sebeple çalışmada yanlış bilgi sınıflandırması, her iki platformla eşleşecek şekilde Warldle'nin (2017) yanlış bilgi kategorizasyonu kullanılarak analiz edilmiştir. Sonuç olarak, her iki platform genelinde yüzde 70.21 hatalı ilişkilendirme, yüzde 11.70 uydurma, yüzde 7.45 manipülasyon, yüzde 4.26 çarpıtma, yüzde 3.19 bağlamdan koparma, yüzde 1.06 parodi kategorilerinde içerikler tespit edilmiştir. Her iki platformda da hiçbir taklit içeriği bulunamamıştır. Mann-Whitney-U testi, her iki platform üzerinden analiz sonuçlarını kontrol edilmiş ve önemli bir fark bulunamamıştır ($U=33,00;p>0.05$).

Sosyal medya platformları etkileşim için gönderilerin çeşitli yönlerden etkileşim almasına olanak tanımaktadır. Twitter'da yanıt (reply), tekrar paylaşma (retweet), beğenme (like), ve paylaşma (share); Facebook'ta beğeni veya yorum; Instagram'da beğeni, yorum, paylaşma ve koleksiyona ekleme (add to collection); TikTok'da beğeni, yorum ve paylaşma özellikleri ile etkileşimde bulunmak mümkündür. Ancak web siteleri için belirli bir etkileşim türü bulunmamaktadır. Web site yapısına ve kuruluşuna göre farklı seçenekler bulunabilmektedir. Ancak, tüm platformlarda çok sık kullanılan bazı etkileşim yaratabilecek yöntemler (klavyede bulunan “#” işareti kullanarak etiketleme- #hashtag (heştek, diyez etiketi), “@” işareti kullanarak etiketleme- tagging, ekran görüntüsü alma, bahsetme) bulunmaktadır. Bilgi doğrulama platformları tarafından analiz edilen gönderiler incelendiğinde, ortalama; 4586 kez tekrar paylaşma (retweet) ve 3691 kez ise diğer türlü (beğen ve yorum şeklinde) etkileşim topladığı görülmektedir. Çok kısa bir sürede krize yönelik yapılan paylaşımların ortalama olarak bu denli yüksek etkileşim alması, yeni medya okuryazarlığının önemini desteklemekte ve yanlış bilgi veya sahte haberlerin yayılımındaki hız konusunda önemli bilgiler sunmaktadır. Tüm bu bilgiler ışığında, bilgilerin/haberlerin doğrulanması için bilgi doğrulama faaliyetlerinin ne kadar önemli olduğu görülmektedir. Ukrayna-Rusya krizi

bağlamında bu platformların paylaşılmış olduğu gönderileri ve sosyal medya üzerinden gelen bilgileri/haberleri doğrulamak için kullandıkları yöntem ve teknikleri bilmek önemli hale gelmektedir. Bu bağlamda, *teyit.org* ve *dogrulukpayi.com* üzerinden yürütülen bu çalışma ile her iki platformda da aynı kategorik, yanlış ve hatalı bilgilerin tespit edilmesi önemli bir bulgudur. Yanlış bilgi veya sahte haberlerin savaş gibi zorlu koşullar altında bile, sosyal medya üzerinden yapılabiliyor olması yeni medya okuryazarlığının önemini bir kez daha vurgulamaktadır. Özellikle fotoğraf ve video içeriği kullanılarak hatalı ilişkilendirme kategorisinde, her iki platformda da veri birikmesi, görsel içeriğin hatalı bilgi/haber paylaşımında kritik bir konumda olduğunu göstermektedir.